

Živa - Easy Live Coding with SuperCollider

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ABSTRACT

Živa is a quark aimed to simplify the live coding experience in SuperCollider, both to quickly set up the environment and to code in a sparse and clear syntax.

This paper describes the reasons that led the author to develop it and his procedures in doing so. The paper introduces the problems encountered when using other languages, and the solutions found in SuperCollider to solve them. This is not a research paper, but a report of the motivation, proceedings and achieved results of the developer's experience in creating this subset of tools for SuperCollider.

1 Introduction

I am not a formally educated programmer nor musician. I'm a professional illustrator, albeit not a formally educated one either.

I do like to play music, and live coding is a great way to create rich and complex music quite easily. With Živa I have found a very good tool for this purpose.

There is, indeed, a full range of live coding languages that have been developed by very experienced software engineers and savvy musicians to be used by pagan and amateur musicians like myself. There's a vast amount of them, and they are all very powerful, robust and created with easy live coding in mind. There's no apparent reason to create a new language for this purpose, and even less apparent reasons for using *sclang*, which is reputed for its confusing and verbose syntax and steep learning curve.

First of all I should clarify that, technically speaking, Živa is more of an eDSL (embedded domain specific language) than it is a complete language. The process that led me to create it came out of need. I have tested many languages, and continue to do so, as I think each one of them enriches my experience as a live coder. Most of the languages I've used rely on SuperCollider running in the background to deal with the actual sound generation and control. Being the SuperCollider user that I am, this may seem a positive thing, because it allowed me to tweak SC if I found the language was lacking a specific feature. And so I did, with every single language I used – I'll get into the details of these lackings in the next section. So I asked myself: why am I always modifying the SC side of any language I use? If they all run SC server in the background, but don't do it the way I like, why not modify the language part of SuperCollider instead? There's another benefit to this approach: it would allow me to live code in one enclosed system only, avoiding the burden, complexity and added problems of using two independent systems that communicate somehow.

SuperCollider is a very versatile language. And I mean the language, *sclang*, not the server (which is awesome). Sclang has a very flexible syntax, which is both good and bad. Most of its bad reputation and intimidating learning curve is caused by this very attribute. Not only there are different ways to achieve the same result, *there are different ways to write the same expression* (SuperCollider, n.d.), and all of them are valid. It seemed reasonable to use this syntax flexibility to create a set of live coding practices and assets that allowed for easier, faster-to-type, and clearer code.

2 Experience with Other Languages

Following is an overview of the languages I've used prior to developing Živa. I found all of them very inspirational, and I have learned something from each one of them. I have shamelessly stolen ideas from all of them, and I am grateful to their developers. Some of them I know personally, and some helped me to solve problems I encountered. On a side note, I encourage all live coders, no matter how inexperienced, to sometime try to develop their own language or set of live coding tools. It is a very enriching experience and I truly think it helps us become better live coding artists.

2.1 ixilang

Ixilang, by Thor Magnusson (Magnusson 2011), is the first live coding language that I learned, back in 2012 (or thereabouts). It was an application that ran *inside* SuperCollider. It opened its own document window (using the discontinued Cocoa library) where the user would type the code. It had short and clear syntax to create patterns, and a set of modifiers that were added at the end of each pattern. Effects could also be applied to both audio and the patterns themselves. This pattern effects changed the code (moved it) to display the actual state of the pattern at any given moment. It was a brilliant piece of software. Unfortunately it died with the deprecation of Cocoa and it no longer works with the current version of SuperCollider.

2.2 TidalCycles

I dare say that, at least in the live coding scene in Barcelona, TidalCycles currently is the most used live coding language. It has a huge and very active community. It's still developed and has a lot of documentation and support. Its pattern approach (McLean and Wiggins 2010) differs a lot from my previous ways of live coding, but I ended up using it for quite a while. It has a short syntax, so it's relatively easy to learn, fast to type, it's clear (if you know the vocabulary) yet surprising and somewhat unpredictable, which I love in a live coding language. It's also very musical, but can get very noisy and experimental, too. The only feature that it lacks, or that it is not very strong at, is audio synthesis. Being a sample-based system, it offers little synthesis capabilities; it's not one of its many strengths.

I do like to use sound synthesis techniques in my compositions and performances, so that's a feature too important to be lacking in my setup. By the time I was using TidalCycles as my main live coding environment, I discovered FM synthesis. It felt frustrating not to be able to play with it in Tidal. With the help from Alex McLean and Julian Rohrerhuber I ended up contributing to SuperDirt and TidalCycles with Superfm, a 6-op FM synthesizer for TidalCycles.

Although this was a great experience, I still didn't feel very much at home with TidalCycles. My mindset has a different configuration, and I must admit that learning Haskell felt a bit too much for me. Also, dealing with two engines didn't look optimal.

2.3 Chucklib

H. James Harkins has developed his own live coding language, *chucklib-livecode* (Harkins [2015] 2020), to suit his needs. He claims that he was also inspired by Ixilang. Chucklib shares a few of ixilang's features and adds his own approach to the track playing/stopping workflow, which is very simple, intuitive and clear. He has also documented it extensively. Reading his code and using it has helped me a lot in my own work with Živa. It seemed a great solution, as it runs in SuperCollider itself.

The problem, though, is that it relies on SuperCollider's *preInterpreter*, which parses Chucklib code and converts it to valid slang syntax in order to be executed. The *preInterpreter* allows to use custom syntax in SuperCollider, but it easily gets in the way if the user wants to mix SuperCollider code with custom code. It can be done, but it's a lot of work and maybe a bit unstable. Although I really appreciate the simplicity and "ixilangicity" of Chucklib, I often found myself wanting to write regular SuperCollider, too. And that eventually led to problems.

2.4 Bacalao

About the same time I started considering my own solution, Glen Fraser started developing Bacalao (Fraser 2022). It is similar to Chucklib in that it also runs in SuperCollider, using the *preInterpreter*. He was inspired by TidalCycles. Although I don't think this might be called a Tidal port for SuperCollider, it shares many of Tidal's idiosyncrasies. It is pattern based, and works with cycles rather than bars.

I offered myself to put Bacalao to the test, but I was discouraged by Fraser’s own reservations, as he intended to use it as his live coding playground and wasn’t specially thinking on a release. He wanted it to be highly experimental, hence unstable. New versions could completely break old code.

Although I’ve kept an eye on it since then, and shared a lot with Fraser (asked for a lot of advice), Bacalao wasn’t ready, at the time, to become my live coding tool for “serious” sessions.

2.5 FoxDot

I do like Python’s simplicity, and a SuperCollider “port” seemed like a promising idea. But FoxDot (Kirkbride [2017] 2021) was, too, lacking synthesis capabilities. And the pattern syntax didn’t feel quite right with the leading P[. . .]. It looked a bit off compared to other Python code, so it was easy to forget for me, and a little uncomfortable. Something extra to think about amidst the mental storm and stress of a live coding set.

2.6 Sonic Pi

Sonic Pi (Blackwell and Aaron 2015) is a great tool for learning live coding, and programming in general. I even taught it to teens and might have performed with it once or twice. I like that it’s simple yet powerful, and it is a self-contained system: it wraps the SuperCollider server transparent to the user, making it simpler to setup and manage. But, SuperCollider is still needed to create and use custom synths.

2.7 Impromptu, Fluxus, Hydra, Orca, etc.

I have tried other languages, like Impromptu (Sorensen and Gardner 2010), Overtone (Aaron et al. [2011] 2019) and Orca (Rabbits [2018] 2019). Coming from the visual arts as I do, I obviously use visual live coding languages. I have tried Fluxus (Griffiths, Papp, et al. [2005] 2010), Hydra (Jack 2023), and even dared live coding shaders with Hexler’s KodeLife (Hexler.net, n.d.).

I especially like Olivia Jack’s Hydra for its simplicity and clarity. It’s amazing and very well documented. It also has inspired me for Živa.

3 My Ideal Live Coding System

This linguistic journey brought up to light my needs and preferences as a performing livecoder. I had, by this time, quite clear what my ideal live coding system would look like. These were my requirements:

- short but clear and versatile syntax
- meaningful syntax namings
- musical expressiveness by means of easy play/stop mechanisms, transitions and parameter tweaking
- self-contained system (language and sound engine in one place)
- sample based and synthesis capabilities
- pattern and modular-patching capabilities
- easy and fast system setup and configuration procedures

All the languages I had tried failed at least in one of these aspects, or needed quite a bit of extra effort to overcome them.

4 Pchain, the Seed of Živa

Going back to SuperCollider as I always was, I decided to look into the possibilities of *sclang*, taking advantage of what first felt a caveat: it’s syntax flexibility.

At this point I was pretty much using patterns as my main tool of composition, so I focused on SC’s pattern library, namely Pbind. I was hoping to find a way to modify any parameter independently, without having to rewrite the hole Pbind definition. I tried different ways, using Pdef, Pdefn, Pbindf, Pset, and more. Although some of them seemed to give me enough flexibility, I always ended up entangled in their intricacies. Until I came across Pchain. Pchain allows

to temporarily overwrite patterns in an additive way. If two Pbinds with different parameters are chained, the result is a combination of both. If any parameter is in both patterns, it gets “overwritten”. The SuperCollider documentation states that Pchain passes values from stream to stream; it sounds a lot like patching a modular synth. The basic syntax is:

```
Pchain(pattern1, pattern2, ... patternN)
```

Values of latter patterns overwrite values of earlier ones. Visually, information travels from right to left. There’s a syntax shortcut for this:

```
pattern1 <> pattern2 <> ... patternN
```

5 Preparing a Modular System

This syntax offered a path to modularity. I could now define a series of musical “atoms” stored in variables that contained a Pbind for each parameter or musical gesture, and combine them at performance time. A minimal setup should include means to modulate amplitude, dynamics, rhythm, stereo panning, ...

This is an example of what it looked like:

```
~acid = Pbind(\instrument, \acid);
~piano = Pbind(\instrument, \piano);

~ff = Pbind(\amp, 1);
~f = Pbind(\amp, 0.5);
~p = Pbind(\amp, 0.2);
~pp = Pbind(\amp, 0.1);

~left = Pbind(\pan, -1);
~right = Pbind(\pan, 1);
~pingpong = Pbind(\pan, Pseq([-1,1], inf));

~faster = Pbind(\dur, 1/4);
~fast = Pbind(\dur, 1/2);
~slow = Pbind(\dur, 2);
~slower = Pbind(\dur, 4);

...
```

When used with Pchain, I was able to combine these elements in a modular fashion, and I could combine it with new Pbind definitions if needed:

```
~acid <> ~p <> ~slow <> Pbind(\octave, 3, \degree, Pseq([0,4],inf));
~piano <> ~f <> ~fast <> Pbind(\degree, Pbrown(0,7,1));
~acid <> ~pp <> ~pingpong <> ~faster <> Pbind(\octave, 7, \degree, Pseq([0,2,4],inf), \legato, 0.1);
...
```

6 Adding Pdef and Ppar

Grouping these inside a Ppar, I could easily create and play different “tracks”. Wrapping it in a Pdef allowed realtime redefinition:

```
Pdef(\a, Ppar[
  ~acid <> ~p <> ~slow <> Pbind(\octave, 3, \degree, Pseq([0,4],inf));
  ~piano <> ~f <> ~fast <> Pbind(\degree, Prand(..7),inf));
  ~acid <> ~pp <> ~pingpong <> ~faster <> Pbind(\octave, 7, \degree, Pseq([0,2,4],inf), \legato, 0.1);
]).play
```

This is the core structure behind Živa. Each line is a “track”, and can be muted by simply commenting the line. As musical expression ideas are worded in variable names, it renders the expressiveness in a comprehensible way. The original Pbind definitions can be used as *presets*, and different copies of the same preset can be modified in parallel. Removing the modifying Pchains, lets the original Pbind play with its unmodified parameters. It’s a very modular system, has short and comprehensible syntax –although readability could be better–, and it’s pure SuperCollider code.

7 Shortcomings

I used this system for quite a while, and got to create musical transitions pretty fluently. But the syntax felt it could be improved: including regular pattern syntax made the code a bit confusing.

And I hadn’t yet tackled the system setup, which was a big deal. Playing synths with SC patterns is pretty straight forward. But samples is a whole story in itself.

8 Live Coding System Setup and Interaction

Živa does actually two things: allows to quickly setup a live coding system and start playing right away; and provides a short language syntax to play expressively and fluently. I’ll divide this section in two parts, each dealing with one of these aspects.

As stated above, playing synths with SC patterns is straight forward. But when it comes to playing samples, it needs some previous work in order to load the samples into buffers, and organizing them in a meaningful way. Playing one sample is not hard; what is difficult is dealing with a library of samples and seamlessly navigating and changing them on the fly.

Živa takes care of all that: it provides functions to load sample collections from directories; stores them in arrays; and prepares a Pbind to play them *ipso-facto*. It does so in a similar way SuperDirt does, most of the code is inspired by it.

Everything is setup when the server is booted with:

```
Ziva.boot;
```

It also provides a series of methods to query the system about its current state, for example: listing loaded samples and synths, instrument control names, available effects names, ... anything that a livecoder on stage would need quick access to. All these are available as class methods of the Ziva class.

Živa comes, too, with a collection of audio effects and provides an effects chain system to route audio through it.

9 Syntax: the Meat of Živa

Finally we get to the main part of this article: the syntax.

Živa’s syntax resides in a few custom pattern classes and event types on one side, and class extensions for SC’s Pattern and SequenceableCollection on the other.

Three new pattern classes have been created: Psynth, Psample and Pmidi. All these are shortcuts to create Pbind instances with the parameters needed in each case, namely the pattern event type (to either play synths, samples or send MIDI messages) and sound name or MIDI device.

Two custom EventTypes are defined: \sample and \ziva_synth. They add default argument symbols to deal with sample manipulation.

I’ll now go over what I believe is the most interesting part of this system: the . dot notation syntax for playing patterns.

9.1 Pattern Types

There are two types of SuperCollider patterns: *event patterns* and *data patterns*.

Data patterns are used to feed data to event patterns. A data pattern is a collection of values that can be sequenced according to the data pattern rules. For example: when the collection is passed to a Pseq it sequences the values in order, one value at a time; Prand plays a random value of the collection on each step; etc.

In order to actually play these data patterns, we need to feed them to an *event pattern*, that will take care of keeping track of time and play the correct data at the correct time.

9.2 Data Pattern Syntax - SequenceableCollection

Regular SC pattern syntax looks something like this:

```
PatternName([item1, item2, item3, ...], repeats);
```

If we want to write an arpeggio that sequences indefinitely it would look like this:

```
Pseq([0,2,4], inf);
```

In Živa the `SequenceableCollection` class has been extended. Any collection, array or list that we would normally feed to a pattern can actually be done so by calling a method. Following is the Živa equivalent for the example above:

```
[0,2,4].pseq;
```

If we need to specify the number of repeats, we can do so by adding it as a function argument:

```
[0,2,4].pseq(3);
```

This implementation always returns a `Pattern` object, so they can be composed with `.` dot notation:

```
[0,2,4].pseq.pstutter(4);
```

Not all SC patterns have been added to this syntax, I'm adding them as I need. But any user could add their own by further extending the class.

I shall briefly deviate from the subject to note that there's a special addition that simplifies the overall syntax burden a little further. It's also a `SequenceableCollection` method that converts an array to a `Pdef(\ziva, Ppar(...))` object using the given list as body of the `Ppar`:

```
[...].ziva;
```

The need for this will come to light after I have explained the new event pattern syntax in the following section.

9.3 Event Pattern Syntax - Pattern

As for event patterns, it extends the `Pattern` class, the parent of all other pattern classes.

The methods added to this class fulfill the role of the `Pchain` usage described above: they atomize `Pbind` parameters and give them meaningful names and allow to temporarily overwrite any other `Pbind` parameters or to add to it. The key concept of the implementation is that every method returns a `Pchain`. This is what provides the `.` notation capabilities also for the `Pbind` parameters.

The basic method implementation is:

```
+ Pattern {  
  methodName { ^Pchain(Pbind(\parameterName, value), this) }  
}
```

For example, to implement the previously stated `Pchain` atoms, and a few new ones, we do it like this:

```

+ Pattern {
  ff { ^Pchain(Pbind(\amp, 1), this) }
  f { ^Pchain(Pbind(\amp, 0.5), this) }
  p { ^Pchain(Pbind(\amp, 0.2), this) }
  pp { ^Pchain(Pbind(\amp, 0.1), this) }

  left { ^Pchain(Pbind(\pan, -1), this) }
  right { ^Pchain(Pbind(\pan, 1), this) }
  pingpong { ^Pchain(Pbind(\pan, Pseq([-1,1],inf)), this) }

  faster { ^Pchain(Pbind(\dur, 1/4), this) }
  fast { ^Pchain(Pbind(\dur, 1/2), this) }
  slow { ^Pchain(Pbind(\dur, 2), this) }
  slower { ^Pchain(Pbind(\dur, 4), this) }

  pizzicato { ^Pchain(Pbind(\legato, 0.1), this) }

  deg { |value| ^Pchain(Pbind(\degree, value), this) }
  oct { |value| ^Pchain(Pbind(\oct, value), this) }
}

```

Then, the usage syntax of the example above becomes:

```

Ziva.boot;
~acid = Psynth(\acid);
~kick = Psample(\trickick); // assuming there's a sample named 'trickick'

(
[
~acid.p.slow.oct(3).deg([0,4].pseq),
~piano.f.fast.deg(..7).prand),
~acid.pp.pingpong.faster.oct(7).deg([0,2,4].pseq).pizzicato,
].ziva;
)

```

If a method provided with this notation is not declared, Živa will pass it over as a Pbind parameter, so there's no need to declare and define methods for each and every new synth. This is kind of a hack, because it overwrites the `doesNotUnderstand` method in Pattern, but I think it's a sacrifice and risk worth taking, given the advantages it provides in this context.

The user can further extend both SequenceableCollection and Pattern classes, customizing them according to their needs.

10 Effects

Last, I'd like to quickly explain the effects chain implementation and the syntax for it.

Živa initializes a dictionary of default effects. When the user needs an effects chain, it creates a track with `Ziva.track("trackName", \effect1, \effect2, ... \effectN)`.

This creates an Ndef with every effect added at the next free slot. For example:

```
Ziva.track(0, \chorus, \reverb, \compress); // numbers can also be used as track names
```

actually is the shortcut for:

```

Ndef(\track_0, {In.ar(bus, 2)}).play;
Ndef(\track_0)[1] = \filter -> Ziva.effectsDict[\chorus];
Ndef(\track_0)[2] = \filter -> Ziva.effectsDict[\reverb];
Ndef(\track_0)[3] = \filter -> Ziva.effectsDict[\compress];

```

To send the audio signal of an instrument to a given effects chain we do it with the `>>` operator at the end of the line, providing the effect trackname or number after it:

```
Ziva.boot;
~acid = Psynth(\acid);
Ziva.track(0, \lpf);

(
[
  ~acid.p.slow.oct(3).deg([0,4].pseq) >> 0,
].ziva;
)
```

11 Conclusion

Although many live coding languages already exist, none of them have all the features I would ideally expect. SuperCollider, in its complexity, allows a great deal of freedom, also in the language syntax domain. Taking advantage of this flexibility allows any user to tailor tools to suit their needs.

Live coding deserves to take advantage of SC's great power, without having to pay the price of syntax verbosity and complexity.

Živa has proved to fulfill this need, by providing a simple way to write expressive musical ideas in a short and meaningful syntax. It allows live coders to quickly set up a live coding system and start using it right away, without sacrificing SuperCollider's audio server's power and existing syntax.

The key to this system relies on two points:

- A custom class, named *Ziva*, that provides a quick interface to boot and setup the server, preparing all the resources needed for the live coder, as well as a collection of methods to interact with it and poll for status information at any point without having to navigate the file system or stop the performance
- An implementation pattern to extend two SuperCollider classes (namely *SequenceableCollection* and *Pattern*) which allows for function composition with the dot (`.`) notation syntax.

The latter is achieved with a very simple concept: to declare and define each custom method with a returning value of the same class.

SequenceableCollection new methods always return a *pattern*; they use the list to feed the newly created pattern and return it to the caller.

Pattern extension methods, on the other hand, always return a *Pchain*, which allows for non-destructive *Pbind* parameter overriding at runtime.

Both of these very basic practices are extremely flexible and easy to learn, hence easy to customize by every live coder willing to do so, as I did.

More than a contribution with a language, this paper aims to contribute to the community with the implementation approach applied on the extended classes. I sincerely think that it may be used in other cases to simplify SuperCollider's intimidating syntax.

12 Acknowledgments

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